

Figure 7. The bacteriophage method seems reliable and efficient for detecting bacterial multiplication in Pfu larger than $10^3/\text{ml}$. □

5. Relation of lesion development and bacterial multiplication in different leaf positions of Zenith inoculated with *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*

Zenith, with *Xa 6* gene for BB resistance, shows resistance from the 11th leaf. It is unclear if bacterial multiplication in susceptible and resistant leaf positions varies. We investigated bacterial multiplication in the 6th, 9th, 10th, and 12th

leaf positions on Zenith using the bacteriophage method.

Six samples from each leaf position were examined at 1, 24, 48, 72, and 158 h after inoculation (HAI). Lesion development was measured at the same time.

On the susceptible 6th, 9th, and 10th leaf positions, lesions began to develop 48 HAI and grew very fast. On the 12th leaf, the lesions were visible 96 HAI, and developed slowly. Two weeks after inoculation, lesion length was 23.6, 18.2, 16.4, and 2.4 cm on leaves 6, 9, 10, and 12 respectively (Fig. 8).

The phage count, expressed as plaque-forming units/cm² leaf area, on leaves 6, 9, and 10 increased 24 HAI, indirectly

indicating bacterial multiplication. Phage count at 48 HAI increased very fast. It peaked at 72 h, then slightly declined. Leaf tissue was totally infected at 120 and 158 h. The phage count on leaf 12 also increased 48 HAI, but was less than on other leaves and declined faster (Fig. 9). □

8. BB lesion development on different leaf positions of Zenith in the greenhouse. IRRI, 1984.

9. Multiplication of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae* on leaves 6, 9, 10, and 12 of Zenith estimated by the phage method. IRRI, 1984.

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Performance of HKR101 under bacterial blight (BB) stress

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HKR101 is a medium-duration semidwarf rice with long bold grains. It was developed at HAU Rice Research Station. We evaluated artificially inoculated HKR101 for BB resistance in a replicated trial from 1980 to 1983. Check varieties were Jaya and PR106.

Whole plots were inoculated 30 d after transplanting by cutting 5 cm from leaf tops with a sickle dipped in inoculum. Inoculum was prepared by soaking 1-cm pieces of infected leaves for 20 min. Al-

though HKR101 was as susceptible to BB as the check varieties, it yielded 16% more (see table). HKR101 has better grain quality than Jaya or PR106, and equal milling recovery. □

Performance of HKR101 under BB stress, Haryana, India.

Variety	BB reaction ^a	Yield (t/ha)					Duration (d)	Panicles/m ²	Kernel length (mm)	Kernel breadth (mm)	Length-breadth ratio	Milling recovery (%)
		1980	1981	1982	1983	Mean						
HKR101	9	5.0	6.0	4.9	3.7	4.9	144	306	7.3	2.5	2.9	66
Jaya	9	4.4	4.9	4.1	3.2	4.2	146	281	6.6	2.6	2.6	66
PR106	9	4.3	5.1	4.4	3.0	4.2	147	292	7.1	2.1	3.4	66
CD at 5%		.8	.9	1.1	.4							
CV %		11.12	10.7	15.97	7.03							

^aIRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice.